

June 30, 2023

<https://ijoabs.com/>

Performance of Finisher Broilers Served Phytogetic Additive (Onion, Garlic and Ginger) In Drinking Water

Author's Details:

¹Favour Bette Patrick Abang, ¹ Emmanuel Ekpo Archibong, ¹Essien Ekpenyong Nsa, ¹Mary Amor Udayi
²Joy Adah

¹Department of Animal Science, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Calabar, Calabar, Nigeria.

²Department of Animal Production, Federal University of Agriculture, Makurdi, Benue State, Nigeria.

Email: abang.favour2@gmail.com

ORCID of corresponding author: 0000-0002-8236-398 Supporting information

Received Date: 30-Apr-2023

Accepted Date: 3-June-2023

Published Date: 30-June-2023

Abstract

A study was carried out to evaluate the performance of finisher broilers served phytogetic additives (onion, garlic and ginger) in drinking water over a period of eight (8) weeks. One hundred and forty four (144) broiler chicks of same weight were randomly allotted to eight (8) treatments in a completely randomized design (CRD). Each treatment was replicated three times with six 6 birds per replicate and a total of eighteen (18) in a treatment. T1 contained water only, while T2, T3, T4, T5, T6, T7, and T8 contained 5g each of onion, ginger, garlic, onion/ginger, ginger/garlic, garlic/onion and onion/ginger/garlic respectively added in 4 litres of water. The result showed no significant ($P>0.05$) differences in feed intake, weight gain, efficiency of feed utilization and body weight across treatments. The study concludes that, the phytogetic additive did not improve the performance of finisher broiler chickens.

Keywords: Phytogetic additive, Drinking Water, Broiler Chicken, Performance indices.

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Poultry birds especially broilers play a significant role in the provision of animal protein required by man to meet his daily protein intake (Maidala and Istifanus, 2012). They have high growth rate, high feed conversion ratio, short generation interval (5-6 months), short intestinal feed transit of 2-3 hours and traits that respond to feeding and nutritional manipulations within few days (Atteh, 2003).

The major constrain of broiler production is cost of feed that accounts for about 70 to 75% of the total production cost (Abang *et al.*, 2013; 2016; 2018). The feed additive could be added to the ration with the purpose to boost animal performance by increasing their growth rate, better-feed conversion efficiency, greater livability and lowered mortality in poultry birds (Rahman *et al.*, 2015). These feed additives are termed as "growth promoters" and often called as non-nutrient feed additives (Singh and Panda, 1992). Many synthetic

June 30, 2023

drugs and growth promoters are supplemented to the broilers to effect rapid growth, but their use have shown many disadvantages like high cost, adverse side effect on health of birds and long residual properties etc.

Growth promoters are chemical and biological substances, which are added to livestock food with the aim to improve the growth of chickens in fattening, improve the utilization of food and in this way realize better production and financial results. With the development and wide use of synthetic and semi-synthetic antibiotics, pros and cons have been experienced throughout the last 50 years, which have been directed research back to natural antimicrobial products as indispensable resources (Rahman *et al.*, 2015).

Through consumption of antibiotic fed broiler the antibiotic residues enters into human body and may cause serious human health hazards with drug residues (Kibria *et al.* 2009). Antimicrobial resistance in zoonotic enteropathogens including *Salmonella*, *Escherichia coli*, and *Enterococci* in food animals is of special concern to human health because these bacteria are likely to transfer from the food chain to humans. Consequently there is considerable research interest in the possible use of natural products, such as essential oils and extracts of edible and medicinal plants, herbs and spices, for the development of new additives in animal feeding (Rahman *et al.*, 2015).

Craig (1999) stated that several phytogetic additives or herbs could help providing some protection against bacteria and stimulate the immune system. Phytogetic are a group of natural growth promoters or non-antibiotic growth promoters, derived from herbs, spices or other plants (Hashemi and Davoodi, 2010) in this context Ginger (*Zingiber officinale*), Gerlic (*Allium sativum*) and Onion (*Allium cepa*). Today, herbs, spices and medicinal plants have received an increasing attention as possible growth promoter's and additives references. There is an evidence suggests that some of these components have different active substances (Al-Kassie and Witwit, 2010). Also, they confer many health benefits to broilers and possess antioxidative properties (Al-Kassie and Witwit, 2010), antimicrobial and it enhance digestion by stimulating endogenous enzymes activity (Dorman and Deans, 2000).

Ginger is the rhizome of the plant *Zingiber officinale*, consumed as a delicacy, medicine, or spice. Preliminary research indicates that nine compounds found in ginger may bind to serotonin receptors which may influence gastrointestinal function. Research conducted *in-vitro* shows that ginger extract might control the quantity of free radicals and the peroxidation of lipids (Al-Amin *et al.*, 2006) and have anti-diabetic properties (Morakinyo *et al.*, 2011).

Garlic has been reported to possess useful pharmacological substances (Rehman and Munir, 2015). Freshly crushed garlic contains alliin, ajoene, diallylsulfide, dithiin, S-allylcysteine. Garlic as natural feed additives in poultry nutrition may be of great benefit and value especially for broiler growers. This is due to their anti-bacterial, anti-inflammatory, antiseptic, anti-parasitic and immunomodulatory properties of garlic (Rehman and Munir, 2015) established that garlic can improve productive performance of broiler chicks.

Onion bulbs possess numerous organic sulphur compounds including Trans-S-(1-propenyl) cysteine sulfoxide, S-methyl-cysteine sulfoxide, S-propylcysteine sulfoxides and cycloalliin, flavinoids, phenolic acids, sterols including cholesterol, stigma sterol, b-sitosterol, saponins, sugars and a trace of volatile oil compounds mainly of sulphur compounds (Aji *et al.*, 2011) noticed the beneficial influence of onion bulbs on growth performance of broiler chickens. Also, Goodarzi *et al.* (2013), Goodarzi *et al.* (2014) and An *et al* (2015) reported that the beneficial influence of onion extracts on the growth performance in meat type broiler chickens.

Objectives

The main objective of this research is to determine the performance of finisher broiler served phytogetic additive in drinking water.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

June 30, 2023

Experimental Location

The study was conducted at the Livestock Teaching and Research Farm, Federal University of Agriculture, Makurdi Benue state. Makurdi is located on latitude 7° 41' N and longitudinal 80° 37' E located in the southern guinea Savannah, zone of Nigeria. It has a raining season that lasts from April to October with an average rainfall of 1200 mm- 1500 mm and the mean temperature ranges from 21°C-30°C and relative humidity with ranges from 47-85% (Dzungwe, 1991).

Preparation of Experimental Test

Garlic, ginger and onion were purchased from North Bank market, Makurdi, Benue state Nigeria. The test ingredients were sliced and sun-dried to a low level of moisture content for prolonged keep. After sun-drying, the ingredients were then ground separately, and tied into labelled leather polythene bags. The birds in the control group T1 were served water without any additive. The powdered phytogenic additive were added to 4 litres of water such that treatments, T2, T3, T4, T5, T6, T7 and T8 contained 5g each of onion, ginger, garlic, onion/ginger, ginger/garlic, garlic/onion and onion/ginger/garlic, respectively.

Table 2: Gross Composition of the Experimental Diet for Chicks

Ingredients	Cp (kg)
Maize	55.39
Soybean Meal	18.55
Fish Meal	4.64
Groundnut cake	9.20
Blood Meal	4.64
Rice Bran	4.00
Bone Meal	3.00
Salt	0.25
Premix	0.25
Total	100.00

Calculated analysis:

Metabolisable Energy (kcal/kg)	2918.10
Crude Protein (%)	24.28
Ether Extract (%)	3.85
Crude Fiber (%)	3.64
Calcium (%)	1.51
Phosphorus (%)	1.05

June 30, 2023

Table 3: Composition of Finisher diet

Ingredients	Cp (%)
Maize	62.51
Soybean Meal	14.99
Groundnut cake	7.50
Fish Meal	3.75
Blood Meal	3.75
Rice Brom	4.00
Bone Meal	3.00
Salt	0.25
Premix	0.25
Total	100.00

Calculated analysis:

ME(kcal/kg)	2980.24
Crude Protein (%)	21.30
Ether Extract (%)	4.61
Crude Fiber (%)	3.53
Calcium (%)	1.39
Phosphorus (%)	1.01

Experimental Birds and Treatments

In this research 150 birds were used. They were housed using intensive system of management. The birds were separated into various treatments using wire mesh cages bedded with wood shavings, which were changed once every week to prevent infection and maintain a hygienic environment for the birds. Drinkers were washed and disinfected daily while the feeders were cleaned daily, washed and disinfected once every week. On arrival having an average weight of 8.65 g, the birds were weighed, separated into 6 birds per cage and then served glucose. Feed and water containing test ingredient were served birds daily. Birds were fed daily; 5g of test ingredient was dissolved in 5 litres of water and served to birds *ad libitum*.

Parameters Measured

The parameters determined were feed intake, weight gain, efficiency of feed utilization, and body weight of the birds.

Statistical Analysis

All data obtained from the study was subjected to one way analysis of variance (ANOVA), using SPSS (2012). Where treatment means were significant ($P < 0.05$) they were separated using the Duncan Multiple Range Test (Duncan, 1995).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Performance

The results of performance indices of broilers served phytogenic additive is presented in Table 4. The value of feed intake ranged from 1231.56 g - 1248.05 g. There were no significant ($P>0.05$) differences across the treatment groups. Bamidele and Adejumo (2012) reported higher range of feed intake (3119.81- 4975.02 g) for growing pullets fed a mixture of garlic and ginger in diets. Similarly, Oleforuh-Okoleh *et al.* (2014) reported a higher range (4652.50 - 5281.50 g) for broiler chickens fed diets containing ground ginger and garlic. The low level of feed intake in this study compared to other studies may be as a result of the influence of ambient temperature, Dagher (1995) reported that ambient temperature has great influence on feed intake of broiler chickens as well as energy content of the feed.

The body weight showed no significance ($P>0.05$) difference, the values obtained ranged from 1533.33-1661.11 g. This result was in agreement with Bamidele and Adejumo (2012) who found no significance difference in the final body weight of pullet served a mixture of garlic and ginger. The body weights of the birds were lower when compared with 1950.00 g - 2475.00 g reported by Oleforuh-Okoleh *et al.* (2014) for broilers fed different herbs. Omer *et al.* (2016) reported a higher range of 23582 - 24621 g for broiler chickens fed diets containing different levels of natural bioactive mixture composed of lemon, onion and garlic juice. An *et al.* (2015) observed a non- significant difference with white mini broilers chickens served diet containing 0.3% or 0.5% onion extract. The low body weight of the birds in this study could be as a result of poor utilization of the feed due to heat stress.

The weekly weight gain was not significantly affected ($P\leq 0.05$). The values obtained ranged from 327.78-362.22 g and was higher than the 261.43-368.57 g reported by Oleforuh-Okoleh *et al.* (2014) for broilers fed different herbs. Bamidele and Adejumo (2012) reported higher value of weight gain with pullets served mixture of ginger and garlic. Esmail (2013) reported that low weight gain could be as an effect of heat stress on the broiler chickens. Efficiency of feed utilization (EFU) was not significantly ($P>0.05$) different across treatments. Result ranged from 3.61- 4.37 and was higher than 2.19-2.53 recorded by Oleforuh-Okoleh *et al.* (2014) for pullets served mixture of ginger and garlic.

Table 4: Performance of Finisher Broiler Chicken Served Phytogenic Additives in Drinking Water.

Parameters	Experimental Diet								
	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5	T6	T7	T8	T8
Initial Body Weight (g)	41.34	40.48	40.64	40.64	41.17	40.64	40.80	41.11	41.11
Feed Intake (g)	1243.17	1242.05	1248.05	1231.56	1236.50	1237.83	1245.78	1238.11	1238.11
Body Weight (g)	1633.33	1590.44	1661.11	1638.89	1572.22	1533.33	1622.22	1622.22	1622.22
Weight gain (g)	327.78	333.33	377.78	362.22	327.78	333.33	316.67	333.34	333.34
Efficiency of Feed Utilization	3.86	3.97	3.85	3.63	3.61	4.16	4.37	4.11	4.11

$\sum X$ = Mean, SEM= Standard Error of the mean, T1 (Water), T2 (onion), T3 (ginger), T4 (garlic), T5 (onion/ginger), T6 (ginger/garlic), T7 (garlic/onion) and T8 (onion/ginger/garlic).

Conclusion

The study concluded that phytogenic additive (garlic ginger and onion) did not significantly improve the performance of finisher broiler chickens.

Recommendation

June 30, 2023

Farmers can incorporate these phytogetic additives (garlic ginger and onion) at higher inclusion levels in the drinking water of broilers to investigate their effect as growth promoters; especially treatments with positive prospect (higher numerical body weights and weight gain values than the control experiment).

REFERENCES

Conclusion

The study concluded that phytogetic additive (garlic ginger and onion) did not significantly improve the performance of finisher broiler chickens.

Recommendation

Farmers can incorporate these phytogetic additives (garlic ginger and onion) at higher inclusion levels in the drinking water of broilers to investigate their effect as growth promoters; especially treatments with positive prospect (higher numerical body weights and weight gain values than the control experiment).

REFERENCES

- i. Abang, F. B. P., Ayuk, A. A. and Okon, B. I. (2013). Growth performance of growing Japanese quails (*Coturnix coturnix japonica*) Fed 48hours Fermented Taro Cocoyam (*Colocasia esculenta var esculenta*) as a replacement for maize. *Indian Journal of Research (PARIPEX)*, 8(3): 34 - 36. ISSN-2250-1991.
- ii. Abang, F.B.P., Aker, D.T and Odunlade, T.A. (2016). Economic of production of growing Japanese quails (*Coturnix coturnix japonica*) fed sun-dried mango (*mangifera indica*) kernel meal. *Global Journal of Agricultural Research*. 4(5)48-55.
- iii. Abang, F. B. P., Egahi, J. O., and Hamber, T. S. (2018). Cost Effectiveness of Anak Broiler Chickens Fed Fermented Mango Kernel Composite Meal as an Alternative Energy Source. *London Journal of science natural and formal*, 18(3): 61-65.
- iv. Aji, S.B., Ignatius, K. Ado Y. and Abdulkarim, A. (2011). Feeding Onion (*Allium cepa*) and Garlic (*Allium sativum*) on some performance characteristics of broiler chickens. *Research Journal of Poultry Sciences*, 4, 22-27.
- v. Al-Amin, Z.M., Thomson, M., Al-Qattan, K.K., Peltonen Shalaby, R. and Ali, M. (2006) Anti-diabetic and hypolipidemic properties of ginger (*Zingiber officinale*) in streptozotocin induced diabetic rats. *British Journal of Nutrition*, 96: 660-666.
- vi. Al-Kassie, G.A.M. and Witwit, N.M. (2010). A comparative study on diet supplementation with a mixture of herbal plants and dandelion as a source of perbiotics on the performance of broilers. *Pakistan Journal of Nutrition*, 9 (1): 67-71.
- vii. An, B. K., Kim, J. Y., Oh, S.T., Kang, C.W., Cho S. and Kim, S.K. (2015). Effects of onion extracts on growth performance, carcass characteristics and blood profiles of white mini broilers. *Asian Australas. Journal of Animal Science*, 28 (2): 247-251.
- viii. Atteh, J.O. (2003). Romancing The Chickens. The sixty eight inaugural lectures series. University of Ilorin, Nigeria. Pp. 131- 145
- ix. Bamidele, O. and Adejumo, I. O. (2012). Effect of garlic (*Allium sativum* L.) and ginger (*Zingiber officinale* Roscoe) mixtures on performance characteristics and cholesterol profile of growing pullets. *International Journal of Poultry Science*, 11(3): 217-220.
- x. Craig, W.J. (1999). Health-promoting properties of common herbs. *American Journal of Clinical Nutrition*, 70 (3): 491-499.
- xi. Dorman, H.J.D. and Deans, S.G. (2000). Antimicrobial agents from plants: Antibacterial activity of plant volatile oils. *Journal of Applied Microbiology*, 88: 308-316.
- xii. Dzungwe, T. A. (1991). The search for a viable Benue State. Sato's Offset Press Nigeria. Pp. 32-35
- xiii. Esmail, S. H. (2013). Factors affecting feed intake of chickens. *World Poultry*, 29(1), 15-17.

June 30, 2023

- xiv. European Commission. (2003). Regulation (EC) N 1831/2003 of the European Parliament and of the Council of on additives for use in animal nutrition. *Official EU Journal*. Pp. 103-122
- xv. FAO. (2011). Mapping supply and demand for animal-source foods to 2030. Animal production and health working paper. Retrieved from <http://www.fao.org/docrep/014/i2425e/i2425e00.pdf> 2: 1-10
- xvi. Goodarzi, M. and S. Nanekarani, (2014). Effect of onion extract in drink water on performance and carcass traits in broiler chickens. IERI Procedia, *International Conference on Agricultural and Biosystem Engineering*, 8: 107-112.
- xvii. Goodarzi, M., Landy, N. and Nanekarani, S. (2013). Effect of onion (*Allium cepa* L.) as an antibiotic growth promoter substitution on performance, immune responses and serum biochemical parameters in broiler chicks. *Health*, 5 (8): 1210-1215.
- xviii. Goodarzi, M., and Nanekarani, S. (2014). Effect of onion extract in drink water on performance and carcass traits in broiler chickens. *International Conference on Future Information Engineering*, 8: 107-112.
- xix. Goodarzi, M., Nanekarani, S. and Landy, N. (2014). Effect of dietary supplementation with onion (*Allium cepa* L.) on performance, carcass traits and intestinal microflora composition in broiler chickens. *Asian Pacific Journal of Tropical Disease*, 4 (1): 297-301.
- xx. Hashemi, S. R., and Davoodi, H. (2010). Phytochemicals as new class of feed additive in poultry industry. *Journal of Animal and Veterinary Advances*, 9(17): 2295-2304.
- xxi. Kibria, K.R.C. and Verma, S.V.S. (2009). Feed additives. Poultry nutrition. Kalyani Publication. Delhi, Pp 140-148.
- xxii. Morakinyo, A.O., Akindele, A.J. and Ahmed, Z. (2011) Modulation of antioxidant enzymes and inflammatory cytokines: Possible mechanism of anti-diabetic effect of ginger extracts. *African Journal of Biomedical Resources*, 9: 195-202.
- xxiii. Omer, H. A. A., Bassuony, N. I., Motawe, H. F. A., and Ahmed, S. M. (2016). Response of broiler chickens to diets containing different levels of natural bioactive mixture composed of lemon, onion and garlic juice. *International Journal of Pharm Tech Research*, 9(12): 892-903.
- xxiv. Rahman, M.A., Ali, M.A., Saha, B.K., Hasan, M.A.A., Rahman, M.A. and Mostofa, M. (2015). Use of neem leaf and ginger extracts for cost effective broiler production. *International Journal of Natural and Social Sciences*, 2(2): 11-16.
- xxv. Rehman, Z. and Munir, M.T. (2015). Effect of garlic on the health and performance of broilers. *Veterinaria*, 3 (1): 32-39.
- xxvi. Singh KS and Panda B (1992). Feed additives. Poultry Nutrition. 2nd. Kalyani publ. Delhi, 134-143.